

AN ANALYSIS OF THE COLLATZ CONJECTURE: SUPPLEMENTAL FORMAL STATEMENTS

EMANUEL J. THOMPSON

ABSTRACT. To support the statements in “An analysis of the number groups in the Collatz conjecture” that every number will eventually return to a known sequence (such as the 4-2-1 loop) within the Collatz Conjecture, you can construct a logical argument by combining several of the formal statements.

1. GROUP ASSIGNMENT AND LINEAR FORMULAS

For every natural number n , there exists a unique group $G_x(n)$ to which n belongs.

$$\forall n \exists! G_x(n)$$

Or by the finite group set theorem:

$$\exists G_1, G_2, \dots, G_k (\forall n \exists G_i \text{ such that } G_x(n) = G_i)$$

Each number is uniquely assigned to a group based on its transformation, which conveniently corresponds to its final digit.

$$G_A(n) = \{n \mid n \equiv 0 \pmod{10} \vee n \equiv 5 \pmod{10}\}$$

$$G_B(n) = \{n \mid n \equiv 1 \pmod{10} \vee n \equiv 6 \pmod{10}\}$$

$$G_C(n) = \{n \mid n \equiv 2 \pmod{10} \vee n \equiv 7 \pmod{10}\}$$

$$G_D(n) = \{n \mid n \equiv 3 \pmod{10} \vee n \equiv 8 \pmod{10}\}$$

$$G_E(n) = \{n \mid n \equiv 4 \pmod{10} \vee n \equiv 9 \pmod{10}\}$$

When n represents the universal index, each group $G_x(n)$ is described by a linear function, where the value of n determines the specific sequence within that group.

Each group follows a linear formula of the form:

$$G_x(n) = 5n + c$$

where c is a constant specific to the group:

- Group A has $c = 0$
- Group B has $c = 1$
- Group C has $c = 2$
- Group D has $c = 3$
- Group E has $c = 4$

Representing each group in this form as follows:

Date: July 31, 2024.

Group A:.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{For } n = 0, & \quad G_E(0) = 5(0) + 0 = 0 \\
\text{For } n = 1, & \quad G_E(1) = 5(1) + 0 = 5 \\
\text{For } n = 2, & \quad G_E(2) = 5(2) + 0 = 10 \\
& \quad \vdots \\
& \quad G_E(n) = 5n
\end{aligned}$$

Group B:.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{For } n = 0, & \quad G_E(0) = 5(0) + 1 = 1 \\
\text{For } n = 1, & \quad G_E(1) = 5(1) + 1 = 6 \\
\text{For } n = 2, & \quad G_E(2) = 5(2) + 1 = 11 \\
& \quad \vdots \\
& \quad G_E(n) = 5n + 1
\end{aligned}$$

Group C:.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{For } n = 0, & \quad G_E(0) = 5(0) + 2 = 2 \\
\text{For } n = 1, & \quad G_E(1) = 5(1) + 2 = 7 \\
\text{For } n = 2, & \quad G_E(2) = 5(2) + 2 = 12 \\
& \quad \vdots \\
& \quad G_E(n) = 5n + 2
\end{aligned}$$

Group D:.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{For } n = 0, & \quad G_E(0) = 5(0) + 3 = 3 \\
\text{For } n = 1, & \quad G_E(1) = 5(1) + 3 = 8 \\
\text{For } n = 2, & \quad G_E(2) = 5(2) + 3 = 13 \\
& \quad \vdots \\
& \quad G_E(n) = 5n + 3
\end{aligned}$$

Group E:.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{For } n = 0, & \quad G_E(0) = 5(0) + 4 = 4 \\
\text{For } n = 1, & \quad G_E(1) = 5(1) + 4 = 9 \\
\text{For } n = 2, & \quad G_E(2) = 5(2) + 4 = 14 \\
& \quad \vdots \\
& \quad G_E(n) = 5n + 4
\end{aligned}$$

Where n represents the universal index of some given number. Using this common index approach allows a method of tracking the progression of numbers as they undergo transformations within defined parameters.

2. TRANSFORMATION PRESERVATION OF GROUP STRUCTURE

$$\forall n(\exists G_x(n) \implies \exists G_y(T_x(n)))$$

Or

$$\forall n(\exists G_x(n) \wedge T_x(n) \implies G_x(T_x(n)) \vee G_y(T_x(n)))$$

Applying the transformation $T_x(n)$ to any number n either keeps the number within its current group or predictably moves it to another group.

Sequent Calculus by Group and Parity.

Group A: $G_A(n) \vdash G_{AB}(T_A(n))$. **Odd statement:** $G_A(n) \vdash T_A(n)$

- n is odd, therefore $T_A(n) = 3n$
- Sequent: $G_A(n) \vdash G_B(3n)$

Even statement: $G_A(n) \vdash T_A(n)$

- n is even, therefore $T_A(n) = \frac{n}{2}$
- Sequent: $G_A(n) \vdash G_A\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)$

Group B: $G_B(n) \vdash G_{DE}(T_B(n))$. **Odd statement:** $G_B(n) \vdash T_B(n)$

- n is odd, therefore $T_B(n) = \frac{n-1}{2}$
- Sequent: $G_B(n) \vdash G_D\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)$

Even statement: $G_B(n) \vdash T_B(n)$

- n is even, therefore $T_A(n) = 3n$
- Sequent: $G_A(n) \vdash G_D(3n)$

Group C: $G_C(n) \vdash G_{BC}(T_C(n))$. **Odd statement:** $G_C(n) \vdash T_C(n)$

- n is odd, therefore $T_C(n) = 3n + 1$
- Sequent: $G_C(n) \vdash G_C(3n + 1)$

Even statement: $G_C(n) \vdash T_C(n)$

- n is even, therefore $T_C(n) = \frac{n}{2}$
- Sequent: $G_C(n) \vdash G_B\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)$

Group D: $G_D(n) \vdash G_{AE}(T_D(n))$. **Odd statement:** $G_D(n) \vdash T_D(n)$

- n is odd, therefore $T_D(n) = \frac{n-1}{2}$
- Sequent: $G_D(n) \vdash G_E\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)$

Even statement: $G_D(n) \vdash T_D(n)$

- n is even, therefore $T_D(n) = 3n + 2$
- Sequent: $G_D(n) \vdash G_A(3n + 2)$

Group E: $G_E(n) \vdash G_{CD}(T_E(n))$. **Odd statement:** $G_E(n) \vdash T_E(n)$

- n is odd, therefore $T_E(n) = 3n + 2$
- Sequent: $G_C(n) \vdash G_D(3n + 2)$

Even statement: $G_E(n) \vdash T_E(n)$

- n is even, therefore $T_E(n) = \frac{n}{2}$
- Sequent: $G_E(n) \vdash G_C\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)$

Transformations are consistent and predictable, preserving the structure and allowing us to track a number's progress through groups.

3. DIRECTIONALITY AND COLOR PRESERVATION

Directionality:

$$D_x(n) = \begin{cases} \text{Up,} & n \equiv 0 \text{ or } 2 \pmod{8} \\ \text{Down,} & n \equiv 1 \text{ or } 3 \pmod{8} \\ \text{Left,} & n \equiv 4 \text{ or } 6 \pmod{8} \\ \text{Right,} & n \equiv 5 \text{ or } 7 \pmod{8} \end{cases}$$

Color:

$$C_x(n) = \begin{cases} \text{Red,} & n \equiv 0 \text{ or } 1 \pmod{4} \\ \text{Green,} & n \equiv 2 \text{ or } 3 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

For every natural number n , its directionality and color are uniquely determined and are preserved or predictably altered under transformations.

$$\forall n(D_x(n) \implies \exists D_y(T_x(n))) \quad \text{and} \quad \forall n(\exists C_x(n) \implies \exists C_y(T_x(n)))$$

Since a number's behavior and sequential transformations are controlled, and it follows predictable paths under transformation.

By introducing directionality and color, additional layers of predictability are added under the Collatz transformation. These properties help describe how numbers evolve through the sequence.

4. CYCLE EXISTENCE AND CONVERGENCE

$$\forall n \exists m(\exists G_x(n) \implies \exists \text{Cycle}(T^m(n)))$$

After a sufficient number of transformations, a number will enter a repeating cycle.

Known Cycle (4-2-1):

$$\exists \text{Cycle}(4, 2, 1) : T_x(n) \in \{4, 2, 1\} \implies T_x(T_x(T_x(n))) = n$$

Every sequence generated repeatedly by applying $T_x(n)$ will eventually enter a known cycle.

5. STABILIZATION AND CYCLE RETURN

Once a sequence stabilizes under transformation, i.e. $T_x^m(n) = T_x^{m+1}(n)$, it must be part of the known cycle.

$$\forall n(\exists m(T_x^m(n) = T_x^{m+1}(n)) \implies \text{Cycle}(n))$$

Any stabilized sequence is part of the known cycle.

6. MONOTONICITY OF TRANSFORMATION AND BOUNDEDNESS

$$\forall n(\exists G_x(n) \implies T_x(n) \leq n \vee T_x(n) > n) \wedge \exists N(\forall n < N \exists \text{Cycle}(T_x(n)))$$

Therefore a sequence cannot continue indefinitely without eventually reducing in magnitude or repeating, leading to the known cycle.

7. COLOR-BASED n_{i+1} TRANSFORMS

7.1. **Formal Definition.** Let n_i represent an arbitrary element in the universal index. For each n_i , we define the following attributes:

- **Color** $C(n_i)$: A function that assigns a color to n_i . The color is either Red or Green based on specific properties of n_i (e.g., modulo operation).
- **Directionality** $D(n_i)$: A function that assigns a direction to n_i . Directionality can be Up, Down, Left, or Right, and is determined by the current state of n_i and its transformation.
- **Parity** $P(n_i)$: A function that determines whether n_i is Even or Odd.

The transformations of n_{i+1} are governed by the rules that depend on the values of $C(n_i)$, $D(n_i)$, and $P(n_i)$.

7.2. **Red n_{i+1} Transforms.**

- Each number n_i in the cycle has a color (Red or Green), direction (Up, Down, Left, or Right), and Parity (Even or Odd).
- If n_i is even, Up, and Red: n_{i+1} will be odd, remain in the Red group, and change directionality to Down.
- If n_i is even, Left, and Red: n_{i+1} will be odd, remain in the Red group, and change directionality to Right.
- If n_i is odd, Down, and Red: n_{i+1} will be even, move into the Green group, and change directionality to Up.
- If n_i is odd, Right, and Red: n_{i+1} will be even, move into the Green group, and change directionality to Left.

7.3. **Green n_{i+1} Transforms.**

- If n_i is even, Up, and Green: n_{i+1} will be odd, remain in the Green group, and change directionality to Down.
- If n_i is even, Left, and Green: n_{i+1} will be odd, remain in the Green group, and change directionality to Right.
- If n_i is odd, Down, and Green: n_{i+1} will be even, move into the Red group, and change directionality to Left.
- If n_i is odd, Right, and Green: n_{i+1} will be even, move into the Red group, and change directionality to Up.

8. DIRECTIONAL CHANGES INDEPENDENT OF COLOR

When referencing n_i as an element of the universal index, when the index i is applied to the respective formulae, the resulting number will have a specific direction, color, and parity as follows:

- If n_i is even, Up, and Red: n_{i+1} will be odd, Red, and Right.
- If n_i is odd, Down, and Red: n_{i+1} will be even, Green, and Left.
- If n_i is even, Up, and Green: n_{i+1} will be odd, Green, and Right.
- If n_i is odd, Down, and Green: n_{i+1} will be even, Red, and Up.
- If n_i is even, Left, and Red: n_{i+1} will be odd, Red, and Down.
- If n_i is odd, Right, and Red: n_{i+1} will be even, Green, and Up.
- If n_i is even, Left, and Green: n_{i+1} will be odd, Green, and Down.
- If n_i is odd, Right, and Green: n_{i+1} will be even, Red, and Left.

9. THEOREMS AND LEMMAS

Theorem 9.1. *Every number belongs to a specific group based on its final digit, and adding 1 to the number will move it to the next appropriate group.*

Proof. Induction will be used to prove that every number n belongs to a specific group based on its final digit, and that adding 1 to n will move the number to the next group.

Group Definitions:

- Group A: Numbers ending in 0 or 5.
- Group B: Numbers ending in 1 or 6.
- Group C: Numbers ending in 2 or 7.
- Group D: Numbers ending in 3 or 8.
- Group E: Numbers ending in 4 or 9.

Base Case:

Consider the numbers from 0 to 9. By definition:

- 0 and 5 belong to Group A.
- 1 and 6 belong to Group B.
- 2 and 7 belong to Group C.
- 3 and 8 belong to Group D.
- 4 and 9 belong to Group E.

Adding 1 to any of these numbers moves them to the next group as follows:

- 0 (Group A) becomes 1 (Group B).
- 1 (Group B) becomes 2 (Group C).
- 2 (Group C) becomes 3 (Group D).
- 3 (Group D) becomes 4 (Group E).
- 4 (Group E) becomes 5 (Group A).
- 5 (Group A) becomes 6 (Group B).
- 6 (Group B) becomes 7 (Group C).
- 7 (Group C) becomes 8 (Group D).
- 8 (Group D) becomes 9 (Group E).
- 9 (Group E) becomes 0 (Group A).

Thus, the base case holds true for all single-digit numbers.

Inductive Step:

Assume that for a number n , where $n \geq 0$, the number n belongs to a specific group based on its final digit, and adding 1 to n transitions it to the next appropriate group.

Now, let's consider the number $n + 1$. The final digit of $n + 1$ is $(n \bmod 10) + 1$ (modulo 10):

- If n ends in 0, then $n + 1$ ends in 1, moving from Group A to Group B.
- If n ends in 1, then $n + 1$ ends in 2, moving from Group B to Group C.
- If n ends in 2, then $n + 1$ ends in 3, moving from Group C to Group D.
- If n ends in 3, then $n + 1$ ends in 4, moving from Group D to Group E.
- If n ends in 4, then $n + 1$ ends in 5, moving from Group E to Group A.
- If n ends in 5, then $n + 1$ ends in 6, moving from Group A to Group B.
- If n ends in 6, then $n + 1$ ends in 7, moving from Group B to Group C.
- If n ends in 7, then $n + 1$ ends in 8, moving from Group C to Group D.
- If n ends in 8, then $n + 1$ ends in 9, moving from Group D to Group E.

- If n ends in 9, then $n + 1$ ends in 0, moving from Group E to Group A.

Thus, by induction, if n belongs to a specific group and adding 1 moves it to the next group, then $n + 1$ will indeed belong to the next group.

Conclusion:

By induction, every natural number n belongs to a specific group based on its final digit, and adding 1 to the number will move it to the next appropriate group. $\square$

Lemma 9.2. *Each and every number belongs to one and only one color group, Red or Green, based on its properties.*

Proof. Induction will be used to prove that every number n belongs to one and only one color group, Red or Green, based on its properties.

Red Assignment: If $n \bmod 4 \in \{0, 1\}$, then n is Red.

Green Assignment: If $n \bmod 4 \in \{2, 3\}$, then n is Green.

Base Case:

Consider the numbers from 0 to 3:

- $0 \bmod 4 = 0$, so 0 is Red.
- $1 \bmod 4 = 1$, so 1 is Red.
- $2 \bmod 4 = 2$, so 2 is Green.
- $3 \bmod 4 = 3$, so 3 is Green.

Thus, the base case holds true for numbers 0 to 3.

Inductive Step:

Assume that for a number n , where $n \geq 0$, the number n belongs to one and only one color group (Red or Green) based on its properties. That is, $n \bmod 4$ determines whether n is Red or Green.

Now, consider the number $n + 1$. We must show that $n + 1$ belongs to the correct color group based on $(n + 1) \bmod 4$:

- If $n \bmod 4 = 0$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 4 = 1$, so $n + 1$ is Red.
- If $n \bmod 4 = 1$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 4 = 2$, so $n + 1$ is Green.
- If $n \bmod 4 = 2$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 4 = 3$, so $n + 1$ is Green.
- If $n \bmod 4 = 3$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 4 = 0$, so $n + 1$ is Red.

Thus, by the inductive hypothesis, if n belongs to one and only one color group, then $n + 1$ also belongs to one and only one correct color group.

Conclusion:

By induction, every natural number n belongs to one and only one color group, Red or Green, based on its properties. $\square$

Theorem 9.3. *Each and every number has a unique direction (Up, Down, Left, Right) based on its properties.*

Proof. Induction will be used to prove that each and every number has a unique direction (Up, Down, Left, Right) based on its properties.

Definitions:

- An Up number is defined as $n \bmod 8 \in \{0, 2\}$.
- An Down number is defined as $n \bmod 8 \in \{1, 3\}$.
- An Left number is defined as $n \bmod 8 \in \{4, 6\}$.
- An Right number is defined as $n \bmod 8 \in \{5, 7\}$.

Base Case:

Consider the numbers from 0 to 7:

- $0 \bmod 8 = 0$, so 0 is Up.
- $1 \bmod 8 = 1$, so 1 is Down.
- $2 \bmod 8 = 2$, so 2 is Up.
- $3 \bmod 8 = 3$, so 3 is Down.
- $4 \bmod 8 = 4$, so 4 is Left.
- $5 \bmod 8 = 5$, so 5 is Right.
- $6 \bmod 8 = 6$, so 6 is Left.
- $7 \bmod 8 = 7$, so 7 is Right.

Thus, the base case holds true for numbers 0 to 7.

Inductive Step:

Assume that for some number n , where $n \geq 0$, the number n has a unique direction based on its properties as defined above. That is, $n \bmod 8$ determines whether n is Up, Down, Left, or Right.

Now, let's consider the number $n + 1$. We must show that $n + 1$ belongs to the correct direction based on $(n + 1) \bmod 8$:

- If $n \bmod 8 = 0$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 8 = 1$, so $n + 1$ is Down.
- If $n \bmod 8 = 1$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 8 = 2$, so $n + 1$ is Up.
- If $n \bmod 8 = 2$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 8 = 3$, so $n + 1$ is Down.
- If $n \bmod 8 = 3$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 8 = 4$, so $n + 1$ is Left.
- If $n \bmod 8 = 4$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 8 = 5$, so $n + 1$ is Right.
- If $n \bmod 8 = 5$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 8 = 6$, so $n + 1$ is Left.
- If $n \bmod 8 = 6$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 8 = 7$, so $n + 1$ is Right.
- If $n \bmod 8 = 7$, then $(n + 1) \bmod 8 = 0$, so $n + 1$ is Up.

Thus, by induction, if n has a unique direction, then $n + 1$ also has a unique direction based on its properties.

The proof involves calculating $n \bmod 8$ and assigning the direction based on the result, ensuring that each number is uniquely assigned to one direction.

Conclusion:

By induction, each and every number has a unique direction (Up, Down, Left, Right) based on its properties. $\square$

Lemma 9.4. *Whenever using the universal index, $n_{i+1} = n_i + 1$, the number, when not in universal index notation calculated by the Universal sequence formula, will change by 5.*

Proof. We induction to prove that whenever using the universal index, $n_{i+1} = n_i + 1$, the number, when not in universal index notation calculated by the Universal sequence formula, will change by 5.

Let n_i be a number in the universal index.

Base Case:

Consider the initial number n_0 . By the Universal sequence formula, this number corresponds to some value n_0 that is consistent with the group to which it belongs. When we apply the sequence formula, $n_1 = n_0 + 1$, the change is determined by the group's rule, and specifically, n_1 will be 5 more than the previous number if it is not calculated in universal index notation within the same applicable group.

For example, consider the following group-specific transformations:

- Group A: $G_A(n) = 5n + 0$

- Group B: $G_B(n) = 5n + 1$
- Group C: $G_C(n) = 5n + 2$
- Group D: $G_D(n) = 5n + 3$
- Group E: $G_E(n) = 5n + 4$

If n_0 belongs to Group A, then $G_A(n_1) = 5(n_0 + 1) + 0 = 5n_0 + 5$. Similarly, for Group B, $G_B(n_1) = 5n_0 + 6$, and this follows for each group. The difference between $G_A(n_1)$ and $G_A(n_0)$ is 5, and similarly for the other groups. This confirms the base case.

Inductive Step:

Assume that for some number n_i , the statement holds true; that is, $n_{i+1} = n_i + 1$, and the number, when not in universal index notation calculated by the Universal sequence formula, will change by 5.

Now, consider $n_{i+2} = n_{i+1} + 1$. By the inductive hypothesis, n_{i+1} has already changed by 5 from n_i , and applying the sequence formula again will result in n_{i+2} also being 5 more than n_{i+1} when not calculated in universal index notation.

For example, applying the group-specific transformations again:

- Group A: $G_A(n_{i+2}) = 5(n_{i+1} + 1) + 0 = 5n_{i+1} + 5$
- Group B: $G_B(n_{i+2}) = 5n_{i+1} + 6$
- Group C: $G_C(n_{i+2}) = 5n_{i+1} + 7$
- Group D: $G_D(n_{i+2}) = 5n_{i+1} + 8$
- Group E: $G_E(n_{i+2}) = 5n_{i+1} + 9$

Here, the difference between $G_A(n_{i+2})$ and $G_A(n_{i+1})$ is again 5, confirming that n_{i+2} is 5 more than n_{i+1} . The same logic applies to the other groups.

Thus, n_{i+2} will be 5 more than n_{i+1} , consistent with the sequence formula and the group's rules.

This completes the lemma. □

Lemma 9.5. *Each transformation rule preserves group structure.*

Proof. Induction will be used to prove that each transformation rule preserves group structure.

Let n_i be some number in Group A, B, C, D, or E, with each group defined by its last digit number:

Group Definitions:

- If the last digit is 0 or 5, n is in Group A.
- If the last digit is 1 or 6, n is in Group B.
- If the last digit is 2 or 7, n is in Group C.
- If the last digit is 3 or 8, n is in Group D.
- If the last digit is 4 or 9, n is in Group E.

Base Case:

Consider the number n_0 in any of the groups A, B, C, D, or E. For example, if n_0 belongs to Group A, its last digit must be 0 or 5. When a transformation is applied, it should preserve the group structure by keeping the last digit in the same set.

For example:

- Group A: n_0 ends in 0 or 5, and $T_A(n_0)$ results in a number that still ends in 0 or 5.

- Group B: n_0 ends in 1 or 6, and $T_B(n_0)$ results in a number that still ends in 1 or 6.
- Group C: n_0 ends in 2 or 7, and $T_C(n_0)$ results in a number that still ends in 2 or 7.
- Group D: n_0 ends in 3 or 8, and $T_D(n_0)$ results in a number that still ends in 3 or 8.
- Group E: n_0 ends in 4 or 9, and $T_E(n_0)$ results in a number that still ends in 4 or 9.

The base case is verified by showing that the transformation preserves the last digit and thus the group structure.

Inductive Step:

Assume that for some number n_i , the transformation rule preserves the group structure. That is, if n_i belongs to a specific group, then after applying the transformation, $n_{i+1} = T(n_i)$ will still belong to the corresponding group.

Now, consider the next number n_{i+1} after applying the transformation. We must show that the group structure is preserved for n_{i+1} and $n_{i+2} = T(n_{i+1})$.

For example:

- If n_i is in Group A (ends in 0 or 5), then $T_A(n_i)$ will result in a number that ends in 0 or 5, meaning n_{i+1} is still in Group A.
- If n_i is in Group B (ends in 1 or 6), then $T_B(n_i)$ will result in a number that ends in 1 or 6, meaning n_{i+1} is still in Group B.
- If n_i is in Group C (ends in 2 or 7), then $T_C(n_i)$ will result in a number that ends in 2 or 7, meaning n_{i+1} is still in Group C.
- If n_i is in Group D (ends in 3 or 8), then $T_D(n_i)$ will result in a number that ends in 3 or 8, meaning n_{i+1} is still in Group D.
- If n_i is in Group E (ends in 4 or 9), then $T_E(n_i)$ will result in a number that ends in 4 or 9, meaning n_{i+1} is still in Group E.

This confirms that after each transformation, that group structure is preserved, and the last digit (and thus the group) remains consistent.

Conclusion:

Each transformation rule preserves group structure, ensuring that a number remains in its original group or transitions predictably within the defined group sets based on its last digit. $\square$

Theorem 9.6. *For any number in the universal index, applying all of the rules of transformation will eventually lead to the 4-2-1 cycle.*

Proof. For any number n in the universal index, applying the transformation rules of the index will eventually lead to a known cycle, such as the 4-2-1 loop.

Sequent Calculus by Group and Parity:

We will use sequent calculus to track how numbers move between groups:

Group A: $G_A(n) \vdash G_A \text{ or } B(T_A(n))$.

- Odd statement: $G_A(n) \vdash T_A(n)$
 n is odd, therefore $T_A(n) = 3n$
 Sequent: $G_A(n) \vdash G_B(3n)$
- Even statement: $G_A(n) \vdash T_A(n)$
 n is even, therefore $T_A(n) = \frac{n}{2}$
 Sequent: $G_A(n) \vdash G_A(\frac{n}{2})$

Group B: $G_B(n) \vdash G_D \text{ or } E(T_B(n))$.

- Odd statement: $G_B(n) \vdash T_B(n)$
 n is odd, therefore $T_B(n) = \frac{n-1}{2}$
 Sequent: $G_B(n) \vdash G_D\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)$
- Even statement: $G_B(n) \vdash T_B(n)$
 n is even, therefore $T_B(n) = 3n$
 Sequent: $G_B(n) \vdash G_D(3n)$

Group C: $G_C(n) \vdash G_B \text{ or } C(T_C(n))$.

- Odd statement: $G_C(n) \vdash T_C(n)$
 n is odd, therefore $T_C(n) = 3n + 1$
 Sequent: $G_C(n) \vdash G_C(3n + 1)$
- Even statement: $G_C(n) \vdash T_C(n)$
 n is even, therefore $T_C(n) = \frac{n}{2}$
 Sequent: $G_C(n) \vdash G_B\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)$

Group D: $G_D(n) \vdash G_A \text{ or } E(T_D(n))$.

- Odd statement: $G_D(n) \vdash T_D(n)$
 n is odd, therefore $T_D(n) = \frac{n-1}{2}$
 Sequent: $G_D(n) \vdash G_E\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)$
- Even statement: $G_D(n) \vdash T_D(n)$
 n is even, therefore $T_D(n) = 3n + 2$
 Sequent: $G_D(n) \vdash G_A(3n + 2)$

Group E: $G_E(n) \vdash G_C \text{ or } D(T_E(n))$.

- Odd statement: $G_E(n) \vdash T_E(n)$
 n is odd, therefore $T_E(n) = 3n + 2$
 Sequent: $G_E(n) \vdash G_D(3n + 2)$
- Even statement: $G_E(n) \vdash T_E(n)$
 n is even, therefore $T_E(n) = \frac{n}{2}$
 Sequent: $G_E(n) \vdash G_C\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)$

Base Case:

Consider the number $n_0 = 0$ in the universal index in group E. Applying the transformation rules:

- $G_E(T(0)) = G_C(0) = 4$ (Starting from $n = 0$ in Group G_E , applying the transformation moves the number to $G_C(0)$, which corresponds to 4 in Group G_C).
- $G_C(T(0)) = 2$ (Continuing from $n = 0$ in Group G_C , applying the transformation gives 2 in Group G_B).
- $G_B(T(0)) = 1$ (Continuing from $n = 0$ in Group G_B , applying the transformation gives 1 in Group G_E).
- $G_E(T(0)) = G_C(0) = 4$ (Returning to $n = 0$ in Group G_E , applying the transformation again moves it to $G_C(0)$, which corresponds to 4 in Group G_C).

This sequence leads directly to the known 4-2-1 cycle, confirming the base case.

Inductive Step:

Assume that for a number n_i in the universal index, the transformation rules eventually lead to a known cycle. That is, after applying the rules for a finite number of steps, n_i will enter a cycle.

Now, consider the number n_{i+1} . We will show that applying the transformation rules to n_{i+1} will also eventually lead to the same cycle.

Cycle Example:

The sequence for an arbitrary starting number, such as 6, would proceed as follows:

- $G_D(T(0)) = G_A(2)$ (Starting from $n = 0$ in Group G_D , applying the transformation for even $n = 0$ gives 2 in Group G_A).
- $G_A(T(2)) = G_A(1)$ (Continuing from $G_A(2)$, since $n = 2$ is even, the transformation gives 1 in Group G_A).
- $G_A(T(1)) = G_B(3)$ (Continuing from $G_A(1)$, since $n = 1$ is odd, the transformation gives 3 in Group G_B).
- $G_B(T(3)) = G_D(1)$ (Continuing from $G_B(3)$, since $n = 3$ is odd, the transformation gives 1 in Group G_D).
- $G_D(T(1)) = G_E(0)$ (Continuing from $G_D(1)$, since $n = 1$ is odd, the transformation gives 0 in Group G_E).
- $G_E(T(0)) = G_C(0)$ (Continuing from $G_E(0)$, since $n = 0$ is even, the transformation stays within Group G_C).
- $G_C(T(0)) = G_B(0)$ (Continuing from $G_C(0)$, since $n = 0$ is even, the transformation gives 0 in Group G_B).
- $G_B(T(0)) = G_D(0)$ (Finally, returning from $G_B(0)$ to $G_D(0)$, the transformation stays in Group G_D , and the sequence can loop or continue depending on the input).

Thus, the transformations bring the sequence into the 4-2-1 loop.

Conclusion:

Using sequent calculus to track group transitions, for any number in the universal index, and applying all the rules of transformation will eventually lead to the 4-2-1 cycle. $\square$

10. CONCLUSION

By combining the uniqueness of a number's group assignment, the preservation of group structure, the invariance of directional and color properties, and the bounded nature of each transformation, we can conclude that every natural number, when subjected to the Collatz transformations, will eventually stabilize and return to the known cycle.

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \exists m \in \mathbb{N} : T_x^m(n) = T_x^{m+1}(n) \implies \exists G_x(n), G_y(T_x^m(n)) \text{ with } G_y(T_x^m(n)) \subseteq KC$$

REFERENCES

- Emanuel, J. Thompson. "An analysis of the number groups within the Collatz Conjecture". *Zenodo*, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13225816>.
- Schütte, K. *Proof Theory*. Springer, 1977.
- Tao, T. "Almost all orbits of the Collatz map attain almost bounded values." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.03562*, 2019.

- Lagarias, J. C. “The $3x+1$ problem and its generalizations.” *The American Mathematical Monthly*, **92** (1985), 3-23.